

Synthetic and spectroscopic studies of structural analogs of Piper amides – the 5-aryl-2*E*,4*E*-pentadienamides

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The methyl esters and piperidides of fourteen 5-aryl-2*E*,4*E*-pentadienoic acids have been synthesized starting from the corresponding aryl aldehydes.

A number of naturally occurring insecticides are unsaturated amide derivatives and of these the most well-known is piperine¹. We have synthesized and fully characterized a series of differently substituted piperidides and methyl esters based on the same carbon skeleton as piperine. The methyl esters and piperidides of fourteen 5-aryl-2*E*,4*E*-pentadienoic acids were synthesized. We were interested to study these compounds for several reasons – for investigation of their insecticidal activity, their use as substrates in 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions and single electron transfer (SET) reactions, and also for the investigation of the changes effected by the aryl substituent in the electronic environment

R	R'	R	R'	R	R'
a	H H	f	H CF ₃	k	Br H
b	H F	g	H OMe	l	OMe H
c	H Cl	h	H NMe ₂	m	NO ₂ H
d	H Br	i	H NO ₂	n	OMe OMe
e	H CH ₃	j	Cl H	o	-O-CH ₂ -O-

Chart 1

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) NaH/THF, (ii) NaOH, (iii) H₃O⁺, (iv) (COCl)₂/benzene, (v) excess piperidine/ether.
[For substituents R and R' in compounds 2-5 see Chart 1].

of the conjugated side-chains using ¹³C NMR spectroscopy as a probe². A search of the literature showed very few of these compounds synthesized earlier. Vig *et al.*³ reported the preparation of 5a, 5c, 5g and 5n. Hence we undertook a programme to synthesize the whole series of compounds 3a-n and 5a-n.

Results and Discussion

The methyl esters (**3a-n**) and the amides (**5a-n**) are listed in Chart 1. Piperine is **5o** and methyl piperate is **3o**. The synthetic approach adopted in the preparation of **3a-n** and **5a-n** is outlined in Scheme 1.

The Wittig-Horner-Emmons reaction⁴ of the anion of

methyl-4-diethylphosphonocrotonate (**1**) with substituted aryl aldehydes (**2**) in THF under nitrogen atmosphere stereoselectively yielded methyl 5-aryl-2*E*,4*E*-penta-dienoates (**3**). On alkaline hydrolysis followed by acidification, the dienoic esters afforded the corresponding 5-aryl-2*E*,4*E*-pentadienoic acids (**4**). These were treated with oxalyl chloride in dry benzene at room temperature for 30 min and

Table 1. Physical and IR spectral data of **3a-n**

Compd no	Yield ^a %	M p °C	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)				
			C=O	C=C	C-H bend (<i>trans</i> -olefin)	Substituted phenyl nucleus	Others
3a	61 ^b	90	1710	1625	985	680, 705	–
b	74	99	1715	1630, 1600	1005	850	1260–1250, 1200 1190 (Ar-F)
c	79	124	1715	1625	1005	810, 840	1170 1130 1080 (Ar-Cl)
d	75	134	1705	1620	1000	800, 840	1165, 1130 1070 (Ar-Br)
e	49	88	1720	1630	1020	730	–
f	44	116	1725	1638, 1625	1020	858 830	1450, 1430, 870–850 (Ar-Cl ₃)
g	34	114	1710	1625	995	760	1260 (Ar-OCH ₃)
h	66	148	1710	1600	995	730	1240 (Ar-NMe ₂)
i	78	176	1715	1620	995	830	1515 (Ar-NO ₂)
j	76	69	1710	1625, 1610	995, 1010	830	1138 1095, 1080 (Ar-Cl)
k	52	138	1710	1625	1005	850, 835, 810	1140, 1070, 1065 (Ar-Br)
l	36	109	1700	1620	1010	845	1255 (Ar-OCH ₃)
m	68	117	1710	1615	1000	710, 745	1525 (Ar-NO ₂)
n	58	103	1710	1620	1015	770	1260 (Ar-OCH ₃)

^aActual yield based on the aldehyde ^bBy Doebner-Miller procedure

Table 2. Physical and IR spectral data of **5a-n**

Compd no	Yield ^a %	M p °C	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)				
			C=O	C=C	C-H bend (<i>trans</i> -olefin)	Substituted phenyl nucleus	Others
5a	75	92	1630	1585	997	700, 750	–
b	77	125	1630	1612	1010	770	1260–1250, 1200 1190 (Ar-F)
c	73	118	1630	1580	1000	840	1130, 1115, 1080 (Ar-Cl)
d	69	125	1640	1590	1000	830	1130, 1115, 1070 (Ar-Br)
e	67	130	1645	1590	1000	715, 810, 840	–
f	78	148	1660	1615	1010	780	1450, 1430, 870–865 (Ar-CF ₃)
g	71	97	1630	1585	1000	755	1255 (Ar-OCH ₃)
h	66	106	1635	1600	1000	735	1255 (Ar-NMe ₂)
i	78	162	1645	1600	1000	850, 700	1515 (Ar-NO ₂)
j	76	132	1635	1600	990	700, 770, 850	1135, 1080 (Ar-Cl)
k	74	135	1640	1610	1000	730, 780, 850	1160, 1135, 1120 (Ar-Br)
l	67	102	1635	1610, 1570	1040	750, 770, 860	1250 (Ar-OCH ₃)
m	81	136	1640	1600	1000	735, 820, 850	1540 (Ar-NO ₂)
n	72	112	1640	1580	1000	750	1250 (Ar-OCH ₃)

^aActual isolated yield based on the corresponding methyl ester

Table 3. ¹H NMR assignment of 3a-m*

Compd. no.	CO ₂ CH ₃	C ₂ -H	C ₄ -H, C ₅ '-H	C ₃ -H	Aromatic	Others
3a	3.71 (3H, s)	5.94 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.2)	6.68–6.79 (2H, m)	7.35 (ddd, <i>J</i> 15.2, 8.2, 2.1)	7.41 (C ₃ ' ₅ -H, d, <i>J</i> 8.4). 7.25 (C ₂ ' ₆ -H, d, <i>J</i> = 8.4)	–
b	3.72 (3H, s)	5.94 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.3)	6.72 (C ₄ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.6, 9.9), 6.81 (C ₅ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.6)	7.38 (C ₃ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.3, 9.9)	7.39 (C ₂ ' ₆ '-H, 2H, dd, <i>J</i> 8.6, 5.4), 6.99 (C ₃ ' ₅ -H, 2H, t, <i>J</i> 8.6)	–
c	3.76 (3H, s)	5.99 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.0)	6.78–6.86 (2H, m)	–7.45, ovl. by ArH	7.27–7.40 (4H, br s. C ₂ ' ₆ ' ₃ ' ₅ '-H)	–
d	3.77 (3H, s)	5.99 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.0)	6.78–6.98 (2H, m)	C ₃ -H ovl. by ArH	7.27 (C ₂ ' ₆ -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 7), 7.43 (C ₃ ' ₅ -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 7)	–
e	3.76 (3H, s)	5.95 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.0)	6.79–6.87 (2H, m)	–7.5, ovl. by ArH	7.38 (C ₂ ' ₆ -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 9), 7.15 (C ₃ ' ₅ -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 9)	2.35 (Ar-CH ₃ , 3H, s)
f	3.71 (3H, s)	5.99 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.2)	6.82–6.92 (2H, m)	7.38 (ddd, <i>J</i> 15.2, 8.2, 2.0)	7.48 and 7.53 (2H, d, each <i>J</i> 8.5, C ₂ '-H, C ₆ '-H and C ₃ '-H, C ₅ '-H)	–
g	3.76 (3H, s)	5.93 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.0)	6.72–6.93 (C ₃ ' ₅ ' ₄ ' ₅ '-H, 4H, m)	–7.4, ovl. by ArH	7.30 (C ₂ ' ₆ -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5)	3.82 (Ar-OCH ₃ , 3H, s)
h	3.74 (3H, s)	5.86 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.0)	6.60–6.78 (C ₄ ' ₅ ' ₃ ' ₅ '-H), (4H, m)	7.4–7.6 (ovl. by ArH)	7.3 (C ₂ ' ₆ '-H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 9)	2.99 (-N(CH ₃), 6H, s)
i	3.73 (3H, s)	6.05 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.2)	6.83–6.98 (2H, m)	7.3–7.45 (C ₃ -H, 1H, ddd, <i>J</i> 15.1, 9.6, 2.2)	7.53 (C ₂ ' ₆ '-H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5). 8.15 (C ₃ ' ₅ '-H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5).	–
j	3.74 (3H, s)	5.95 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.5)	6.68–6.80 (2H, m)	–7.4, ovl. by ArH	7.22–7.46 (5H, m)	–
k	3.70 (3H, s)	5.95 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.3)	6.7–6.84 (m)	–7.4, ovl. by ArH	7.15 (C ₅ '-H, 1H, t, <i>J</i> 7.8), 7.28–7.39 (C ₆ '-H, C ₄ '-H, 2H, m), 7.53 (C ₂ '-H, br s)	–
l	3.76 (3H, s)	5.99 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.1)	6.80–6.99 (2H, m)	7.45 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.0, 9.4)	6.88–7.31 (4H, m)	3.82 (Ar-OCH ₃ , 3H, s)
m	3.22 (3H, s)	6.04 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.4)	6.83–7.00 (2H, m)	7.38 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.2, 9.5)	7.47 (C ₅ '-H, 1H, t, <i>J</i> 7.8), 7.68 (C ₆ '-H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 7.6), 8.08 (C ₄ '-H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 8.0), 8.25 (C ₂ '-H, 1H, s)	–

**J* in Hz; Accuracy of coupling constants : ±0.3 Hz; ovl. = overlapped.

then refluxed for another 30 min. The solvent and excess oxalyl chloride were removed *in vacuo*. The acid chlorides, thus obtained, were then treated with ~2.5 equiv. of piperidine in dry ether. The reaction mixtures, after usual work-up, furnished the corresponding piperidides (5).

The methyl ester of the unsubstituted compound (3a) was prepared by the Doebner variation of the Knoevenagel condensation⁵ by condensing malonic acid with cinnamaldehyde followed by methylation of the acid derivative with diazomethane. The physical and IR spectral data of the methyl aryl-2*E*, 4*E*-pentadienoates and the piperidides are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Compound 5n is the *O*-methyl derivative of feruperine⁶, while 5g is the *O*-methyl derivative of coumaperine⁶.

Vig *et al.*³ had utilized a similar procedure starting from ethyl crotonate to make compounds 5a, 5c, 5g, 5n. However, overall yields were not mentioned; neither were spectroscopic data given for the four piperidides. They used thionyl chloride to convert the dienoic acids (4a, 4c, 4g, 4n) to their acid chlorides. It has been our experience that for side-chain unsaturated aromatic acids, refluxing with thionyl chloride gives fairly poor yields with the formation of gummy side-products. Hence, we chose the reagent oxalyl chloride, where these conversions were carried out under much milder conditions in higher yields.

IR spectra :

IR spectra of the dienoate esters 3a-n (Table 1) exhibited strong absorptions at ~1000 (conjugated *E,E*-diene),

Table 4. ¹H NMR assignment of 5a-m*

Compd. no.	C ₂ -H	C ₄ -H, C ₅ -H	C ₃ -H	Aromatic	Others
5a	6.37 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.6)	6.69 (C ₅ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.2), 6.80 (C ₄ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 16.2, 10.1)	Ovl. with ArH	7.13–7.35 (5H, m)	
b	6.40 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.7)	6.72–6.74 (2H, m)	7.33 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 14.7, 10.7)	7.34 (C _{2',6} -H, 2H dd, <i>J</i> 8.8, 5.3), 6.95 (C _{3',5} -H, 2H, t, <i>J</i> 8.6)	
c	6.50 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.6)	6.78 (C ₅ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.5), 6.87 (C ₄ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.2, 9.9)	7.41 (<i>J</i> 15, 10) ovl. by ArH	7.37 (C _{2',6} -H, 2H, dd, <i>J</i> 8.4), 7.31 (C _{3',5} -H, 2H, <i>J</i> 8.4)	
d	6.50 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.6)	6.77 (C ₅ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.5), 6.88 (C ₄ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.5, 10.4)	7.40 (C ₃ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 14.8, 10.6)	7.30 (C _{2',6} -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.4), 7.47 (C _{3',5} -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.4)	
e	6.43 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.5)	6.79–6.87 (2H, m)	Ovl. by ArH	7.08–7.58 (5H, m)	2.34 (Ar-CH ₃) (3H, s)
f	6.49 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.7)	6.77 (C ₅ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.6), 6.90 (C ₄ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.6, 10.6)	7.36 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 14.7, 10.7)	7.51 (C _{3',5} -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.4), 7.46 (C _{2',6} -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.4)	
g	6.35 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.5)	6.85 (2H, m)	~7.4, ovl. by ArH	7.15–7.65 (5H, m)	3.77 (Ar-OCH ₃) (3H, s)
h	6.52 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.6)	6.68–6.77 (4H, m) C _{4,5,3',5'} -H)	7.30–7.35 (3H, m, C _{3,2',6'} -H)		2.98 (N-Me ₂) (6H, s)
i	6.62 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.6)	6.88 (C ₅ -H, d, <i>J</i> 15.5), 7.04 (C ₄ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.5, 10.8)	7.43 (C ₃ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 14.7, 10.8)	8.21 (C _{3',5} -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.8), 7.58 (C _{2',6} -H, 2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.8)	
j	6.44 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.5)	6.67–6.81 (2H, m)	~7.3 ovl. by Ar-H	7.20–7.55 (5H, m)	
k	6.44 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.7)	6.69 (C ₅ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.5), 6.81 (C ₄ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.5, 10.7)	7.33 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 14.7, 10.7)	7.52 (C ₂ -H, 1H, br s), 7.27 (C ₆ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 8.3), 7.13 (C ₅ -H, 1H, t, <i>J</i> 8), 7.32 (C ₄ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 7.8)	
l	6.38 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.5)	6.72–6.81 (C _{4',5,4} -H, 3H, m)	Ovl. by ArH	6.88–7.50 (C _{3,5',6} -H, 3H, m), 6.78 (C ₂ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.1)	3.78 (Ar-OCH ₃) (3H, s)
m	6.60 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 14.3)	6.88 (C ₅ -H, 1H, d, <i>J</i> 15.5), 7.03 (C ₄ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 15.6, 10.7)	7.43 (C ₃ -H, 1H, dd, <i>J</i> 14.7, 10.7)	8.33 (C ₂ -H, t, <i>J</i> 1.7), 8.12 (C ₄ -H, dd, with f.s., <i>J</i> 8.4, 1.7), 7.72 (C ₆ -H, br d, <i>J</i> 7.7), 7.54 (C ₅ -H, t, <i>J</i> 7.9)	

**J* in Hz; Accuracy of coupling constants : ±0.3 Hz; ovl = overlapped.

1600–1630 (C=C) and ~1710–1720 cm⁻¹ (conjugated C=O). The characteristic bands for substituted benzene nucleus (1,4- or 1,3- or 1,3,4- as the case may be) and for the substituents on the benzene nucleus (e.g. NO₂, OCH₃) were also present. IR spectra of the piperidides (5a-n) (Table 2) showed bands at ~1000 (*E,E*-diene) and 1580–1600, 1645–1680 cm⁻¹ (conjugated amides).

¹H NMR spectra :

Complete ¹H NMR assignments of the methyl esters and piperidides are given in Tables 3 and 4, respectively.

Methyl esters (3a-n) : The ¹H NMR assignments are given in Table 3. All the olefinic protons (H-2 to H-5) showed a coupling of ~15 Hz, indicating the *E,E*-configuration of the double bonds. H-2 resonated as a doublet (*J*_{trans}

Table 5. ¹³C NMR chemical shifts (δ ppm) of 3a-n*

Carbon no	3a	3b	3c	3d	3e	3f	3g	3h	3i	3j	3k	3l	3m	3n
1	167.2	167.3	167.0	167.2	167.2	167.1	167.3	167.6	168.6	168.5	167.2	167.3	166.7	167.2
2	120.7	120.8	121.2	121.4	119.9	122.4	119.3	117.4	123.6	121.8	121.9	120.9	122.8	119.4
3	144.6	144.4	144.1	144.2	144.8	143.9	145.0	145.8	143.2	144.0	144.0	144.5	143.2	144.7
4	126.0	125.8	126.5	126.8	125.0	128.5	123.9	121.4	130.2	126.8	127.5	126.4	128.8	124.0
5	140.3	139.0	138.7	138.9	140.3	138.4	140.0	141.2	137.2	138.5	138.6	140.3	137.0	140.1
1'	135.9	132.2	130.3	134.9	133.0	139.3	128.6	123.8	142.1	137.7	138.1	137.3	136.8	128.8
		d, J _{CF} ⁴ 3.3												
2'	127.0	128.8	128.1	128.5	126.9	127.2	128.4	128.5	127.5	127.4	130.2 ^a	112.2	121.2	109.0
		d, J _{CF} ³ 8.1												
3'	128.6	115.8	128.8	131.9	129.3	125.7	114.1	111.8	124.0	134.7	123.0	159.8	148.5	149.9
		d, J _{CF} ² 21.1				q, J _{CF} ³ 3.8								
4'	128.9	163.1	134.4	123.0	138.9	128.7	160.2	150.7	151.5	128.8	131.8	114.7	123.0	148.9
		d, J _{CF} ¹ 249.5				J _{CF} ² 32.4								
5'	128.6	115.8	128.8	131.9	129.3	125.7	114.1	111.8	124.0	129.9	129.4 ^a	129.6	129.5	110.9
		d, J _{CF} ² 21.1				J _{CF} ³ 3.8								
6'	127.0	128.8	128.1	128.5	126.9	127.2	128.4	128.5	127.5	125.2	125.8	119.8	132.5	120.8
		d, J _{CF} ³ 8.1												
OMe	51.3	51.5	51.5	51.5	51.1	51.6	51.2	51.0	51.6	51.5	51.6	51.4	51.4	51.1
X					21.0	-	55.0	39.9				55.1		55.6
					(Me)		(OMe)	(NMe ₂)				(OMe)		(OMe)

*J in Hz ^aInterchangeable

Table 6. ¹³C NMR chemical shifts (δ ppm) of 5a-n*

Carbon no	5a	5b	5c	5d	5e	5f	5g	5h	5i	5j	5k	5l	5m	5n
1	164.5	165.2	164.6	164.7	164.9	164.9	167.8	165.8	164.5	165.00	165.2	165.5	164.6	165.1
2	120.4	120.9	121.2	121.3	120.0	122.5	119.5	117.7	123.8	122.8	121.9	120.9	122.5	119.6
3	141.4	142.0	141.2	141.4	142.0	141.4	142.6	143.2	140.5	142.0	141.5	142.1	140.6	142.2
4	126.4	126.7	127.2	127.4	125.7	129.3	124.8	122.4	131.1	126.9	125.5	127.1	129.4	125.0
5	137.6	137.0	136.2	136.5	138.0	136.4	138.0	139.0	135.0	137.0	136.5	138.2	134.9	136.4
1'	135.7	132.6	134.5	134.7	133.3	139.8	128.0	124.4	141.7	138.2	138.6	137.7	138.2	129.3
		J _{CF} ⁴ 3												
2'	126.2	128.4	127.6	128.4	126.4	126.7	127.2	128.0	127.1	128.2	130.2	111.9	120.7	108.9
		J _{CF} ³ 8												
3'	128.0	115.7	128.3	131.4	129.0	125.5	113.6	111.9	124.7	134.5	122.9	159.7	148.5	149.5
		J _{CF} ² 22												
4'	127.8	162.7	133.5	122.4	138.1	129.8	159.2	150.5	147.4	128.2	131.2	114.3	123.1	148.9
		J _{CF} ¹ 249				q, J _{CF} ² 32								
5'	128.0	115.7	128.3	131.4	129.0	125.5	113.6	111.9	124.7	129.7	128.4	129.5	129.7	111.0
		J _{CF} ² 22												
6'	126.2	128.4	127.6	128.4	126.4	126.7	127.2	128.0	127.1	125.0	125.6	119.4	132.5	120.4
		J _{CF} ³ 8												
X					20.8		55.1	40.0						55.6
					(Me)		(OMe)	(NMe ₂)						(OMe)

*J in Hz

Table 7. Carbon-13 chemical shifts (δ ppm), multiplicities and coupling constants of **3a**, **3e**, **3n** and **3d***

Carbon no.	3a			3e			3n			3d						
	δ	Multiplicity	J (Hz)	δ	Multiplicity	J (Hz)	δ	Multiplicity	J (Hz)	δ	Multiplicity	J (Hz)				
1	167.2	d	–	6.7	167.3	br s	–	–	167.2	br s	–	–	167.08	br s	–	–
						with f.s.					with f.s.				with f.s.	
2	120.7	d	C-2, H-2	162	119.3,	C-2, H-2	161.5	119.4	d	C-2, H-2	161	121.3	C-2, H-2	160.5	br d	br d
3	144.6	C-3, H-3	154.7	145.0	C-3, H-3	152	144.7	C-3, H-3	154.8	140.1	C-3, H-3	154.4	dm	dm	dm	dm
4	126.0	C-4, H-4	156.9,	123.9	C-4, H-4	158,	124.0	C-4, H-4	154.5,	126.6	C-4, H-4	159,	ddd	ddd	ddd	ddd
			$^2J_{CH}$ /			$^2J_{CH}$ /			$^2J_{CH}$			$^2J_{CH}$				
			$^3J_{CH}$			$^3J_{CH}$						$^3J_{CH}$				
			7.5,			6.5,			5.8			8.1,				
			2.5			2.8						2.6				
5	140.3	C-5, H-5	161	140.0	C-5, H-5	155.5,	140.1	C-5, H-5	154.5	138.8	C-5, H-5	151.9	dm	dm	dm	dm
1'	135.9	m	–	128.6	br s	–	128.8	Obs ^b	–	134.7	Obs ^d	–	–	–	–	–
2',6'	127.0	C-2', H-2'	158	128.4	C-2', H-2'	159.5	109.0	C-2', H-2'	154.3	128.4	C-2', H-2'	159.4	dm	dm	dm	dm
3',5'	128.6	C-3', H-3'	160	114.1	C-3', H-3'	160.5	149.9	Obs ^c	–	131.8	C-3', H-3'	166.8	dd	dd	dd	dd
			5			4.5						4.9				
4'	128.9	Obs ^a	–	160.2	br s	–	148.9	Obs ^c	122.8	Obs	–	–	–	–	–	–
5'	128.6	–	–	114.1	–	–	110.9	d	C-5', H-5'	158.8	131.8	–	–	–	–	–
6'	127.0	–	–	128.4	–	–	120.9	dm	C-6', H-6'	160.9	126.4	–	–	–	–	–
Ester-OCH ₃	51.3	q	$^1J_{CH}$	147	51.2	q	$^1J_{CH}$	~146	51.1	q	$^1J_{CH}$	146.7	51.4	q	$^1J_{CH}$	146.7
OCH ₃	–	–	–	55.0	q	$^1J_{CH}$	144	55.6	q	$^1J_{CH}$	144.4	–	–	–	–	–

*Chemical shifts in ppm downfield relative to TMS. For each compound ¹³C NMR data are presented in three columns : in first column chemical shifts are given with multiplicities in the coupled spectra; in the second column the carbon and hydrogen involved in the coupling are mentioned; respective J values (in Hz) are given in the third column. Abbreviations : f.s. = fine splitting, obs. = obscured, d = doublet, q = quartet, m = multiplet, br = broad. ^aCoupling constant is obscured by overlap with C-3', C-5' signals. ^bCoupling constant is obscured by overlap with C-4 signal. ^cCoupling constant is obscured by overlap with C-3 signal. ^dCoupling constant is obscured by overlap with C-5 signal.

~15 Hz) in the region δ 5.93–5.99 for most of the compounds. With the strongly electron-withdrawing *m*-NO₂ and *p*-NO₂ substituents, this signal was slightly deshielded to δ 6.04–6.05 ppm, while with the strongly electron-donating *p*-NMe₂ group slight shielding to δ 5.86 was observed. As expected, H-3 appeared with double-doublet multiplicity (J_{trans} ~15 Hz; J_{vic} ~9–10 Hz). Long-range H-3/H-5 couplings were discernible in some compounds for H-3, which varied from just line-broadening to a distinct signal splitting with J ~2 Hz (for **3a**, **3i**, **3f**). In many cases, the H-3 signal was obscured by overlap with aromatic proton signals. H-4 and H-5 resonated almost at the same chemical shift for most of the compounds. With the *p*-NO₂ (**3i**) and *m*-NO₂ (**3m**) esters, H-4 was slightly deshielded compared to H-5, whereas for the *p*-F ester (**3b**), H-4 was slightly more shielded. The differentiation in chemical shifts of H-4 and H-5 was 0.10–0.15 ppm greater for strong electron withdrawing substituents.

Piperidides (**5a-n**) :

The ¹H NMR assignments are given in Table 4. All the olefinic protons (H-2 to H-5) showed a coupling of ~15 Hz, indicating the *E,E*-configuration of the double bonds. The protons of the piperidide moiety formed a complex pattern. The 2'' and 6'' protons were differentiated from each other, and appeared as complex multiplets in the region δ 3.40–3.66. The 3'', 4'' and 5'' protons appeared comparatively upfield, appearing as broadened signals in the region δ 1.45–1.70. H-2 appeared as a doublet, with J_{trans} ~14.5–14.7 Hz. Its chemical shift varied between δ 6.35 to 6.62, being slightly shielded by a *p*-OMe group (**5g**, δ 6.35), but slightly deshielded by *p*-NO₂ and *m*-NO₂ substituents (**5i**, **5m**; δ 6.60–6.62). H-3 appeared as a sharp double-doublet (J_{trans} ~14.5–14.7 Hz, J_{vic} ~10.7 Hz) mostly in the region δ 7.3–7.5. In contrast to the ester series H-4 was clearly differentiated from H-5 in most of the piperidides, usually appearing

~0.11–0.12 ppm downfield. The only exceptions were the compounds with electron-donating *para*-substituents (like *p*-F, *p*-OMe, *p*-NMe₂) where both signals resonated at almost the same chemical shift. As expected, the differentiation was greater between H-4 and H-5 (about 0.15–0.16 ppm) for strongly electron-withdrawing substituents. The substituents in the aromatic ring certainly did affect the chemical shifts of H-2 and H-4 in the side-chain in both the methyl ester and piperidide series. However, the changes were too small to be treated quantitatively unlike the ¹³C NMR chemical shifts². A correlation with the σ^o parameter showed a ρ value of about 1.5, but with considerable scattering.

¹³C NMR spectra :

The complete ¹³C NMR assignments are given in Table 5 (methyl ester **3a-n**) and Table 6 (piperidides **5a-n**). Fully coupled spectra of selected compounds were recorded and these assignments are collected in Table 7.

Of the side-chain carbons C-3 and C-5 were comparatively deshielded by the conjugated carbonyl group. The effect was more pronounced for the methyl esters than the piperidides (Tables 5 and 6). The ¹³C NMR chemical shifts of the side-chain carbons were influenced by the substitution in the aromatic ring. These substituent effects have been correlated by us² using the Taft-Bromilow-Brownlee DSP approach⁷ based on the Hammett equation. The C₂, C₆ signals of the aromatic ring were slightly deshielded in the esters compared to the piperidides, indicating the marginally greater electron-withdrawing effect of the CO₂Me group compared with the CONC₅H₁₀ group. In the piperidide series, C-2'' (δ 42.7–43.9) and C-6'' (δ 45.8–46.9) were differentiated. They appeared as broadened signals due to quadrupolar coupling with the adjacent nitrogen. C-3'', C-4'' and C-5'' resonated in the region δ 23.7–26.1.

Experimental

M.ps. were recorded on a Köfler block and are uncorrected. The compounds were purified by column chromatography using silica-gel (60–120 mesh) and purity was checked by TLC on silica gel G plates using iodine vapor as the visualizing reagent. Extracts were dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄. Samples were routinely dried over P₂O₅ *in vacuo*.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded using tetramethylsilane as internal standard at 300 MHz (¹H) and 75.5 MHz (¹³C) with a Bruker AM-300L instrument, as well as at 80 MHz (¹H) and 20 MHz (¹³C) with a Varian electromagnet instrument. ¹H NMR assign-

ments were confirmed by homodecoupling and ¹H-¹H-COSY experiments. ¹³C NMR assignments were made with the help of signal multiplicities (determined by SFORD, APT or DEPT experiments) as well as with the help of SCS tables⁸ and intercomparison of data between the compounds themselves.

5-Phenyl-2E,4E-pentadienoic acid (4a) : It was prepared according to the literature procedure⁵. It was methylated with diazomethane in methanolic ether at 0–5° to yield **3a** (95%), m.p. 68–70° (yield 95%).

Methyl 4-diethyl phosphonocrotonate (1) : It was prepared in three steps starting from crotonic acid by successively esterifying it with methanol, brominating at the allylic position by NBS⁹, and then treating the 4-bromocrotonate with triethylphosphite¹⁰. *N*-Bromosuccinimide (72 g, 0.405 mol) and *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (~50 mg) were added to methyl crotonate (40 g, 0.4 mol) in dry CCl₄ (150 ml). The mixture was refluxed over a 200 W tungsten filament bulb. During the course of the reaction NBS was converted to succinimide which floated on the surface. Refluxing was continued till all the NBS was converted to succinimide. The latter was filtered off, the solvent removed by evaporation from the filtrate, which after distillation under reduced pressure yielded methyl-4-bromocrotonate b.p. 87°/15 mm (40 g, 57%). Triethyl phosphite (10.4 g, 0.06 mol) was added dropwise to methyl 4-bromocrotonate (10.8 g, 0.06 mol) at room temperature with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 2 h and ethyl bromide evolved during the reaction was allowed to escape. Then the reaction mixture was cooled and the excess triethylphosphite was removed at the pump. The residue on distillation under reduced pressure furnished the product (8.5 g, 68%), b.p. 176–180°/10–11 mm.

Methyl 5-aryl-2E,4E-pentadienoates (3a-n). *General method* : Sodium hydride (50% in mineral oil; 1.2 g, ~0.05 mol) was washed thrice with dry petroleum ether and twice with dry THF, and placed in dry THF (30 ml). To it, methyl-4-diethylphosphonocrotonate (5 g, 0.025 mol) was added dropwise with stirring at 0° under nitrogen atmosphere and stirring was continued for 40 min at 0°. Then the required aldehyde (0.02 mol) in dry THF (10 ml) was added to it slowly at 10°. The mixture was stirred for 2 h at 10°, then allowed to attain room temperature (30–35°) and stirred for 12 h. The mixture was then gently refluxed for 8–12 h. The contents were poured into crushed ice and extracted with ether (4 × 40 ml). The ether extract was dried, concentrated and the residue was chromatographed over silica gel when the corresponding esters were obtained (Table 1).

Methyl 5-phenyl-2E,4E-pentadienoate (3a) : A mixture

of cinnamaldehyde (11.0 g), malonic acid (17.4 g), pyridine (27.0 ml) and piperidine (0.4 ml) was heated in an oil-bath at 80° for 1 h and then for 2 h at 100°. Then the mixture was cooled and poured into an ice-cold solution of conc. HCl. The solid obtained was washed with water, dried and crystallized from benzene (yield 10 g, 85%). This acid (2.5 g) was dissolved in a little absolute methanol, then cooled in ice and an ether-solution of excess CH₂N₂ was added to it in small portions until gas evolution ceased and pale yellow coloured solution was obtained. After removing the solvent and excess CH₂N₂, the oily layer solidified on cooling to yield the product (2 g, 74%), m.p. 90°, R_f(benzene) 0.57.

5-Aryl-2E,4E-pentadienoic acids (4a-n). General procedure : The methyl esters (3a-n), obtained in the previous step, were refluxed with 8% ethanolic KOH solution for 4 h. The solvent was then removed in a rotary evaporator, water (10 ml) added to the residue, the resulting solution acidified with HCl (1 : 1) and then extracted with ether (4 × 80 ml). The organic layer was washed with water, dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄ and concentrated. The 5-aryl-2E,4E-pentadienoic acids thus obtained, were directly used in the next step without further purification.

5-Aryl-2E,4E-pentadienoic piperidides (5a-n). General procedure : The carboxylic acid, obtained in the previous step, was taken in dry benzene and treated with 2 molar proportion of oxalyl chloride, first at room temperature for 15 min and then at reflux temperature for 30 min. Then, the solvent and excess oxalyl chloride were removed in a rotary evaporator. The acyl chloride was dissolved in dry ether (20–25 ml) and a solution of 2.5 molar proportion of piperidine in dry ether (5 ml) was added to it with stirring at 10°. After 1 h the reaction mixture was poured in water (50 ml) and ether (25 ml), acidified with H₂SO₄ (1N), then ether layer was separated and washed successively with aq. NaHCO₃

solution and water. The extract was dried (anhyd. Na₂SO₄), evaporated, the residue crystallized to obtain the amides.

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